

Assessment of Temperature Feedback Models for Point-Kinetics in Heat Pipe–Cooled Microreactors

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ABSTRACT

Heat pipe–cooled microreactors (HPMRs) are strong candidates for remote applications due to their passive heat removal and robust negative reactivity feedback. Point-kinetics Equation (PKE) models are commonly used to simulate transient behavior in HPMRs. PKE simulations depend on temperature-dependent reactivity models to represent thermal feedback, yet these reactivity models have received limited verification against high-fidelity solutions for HPMRs. This study evaluates the accuracy of four PKE temperature–reactivity models by comparing their predictions with high-fidelity reference calculations from the Griffin deterministic neutronics code and MOOSE thermal solver. Using the realistic HPMR (rHPMR) benchmark, all kinetics parameters are derived from consistent DFEM- S_n calculations, and model performance is assessed for an unprotected loss-of-heat-sink (ULOHS) transient. Results show that the commonly used constant-coefficient model introduces significant errors in both reactivity and temperature predictions. In contrast, linear and nonlinear regression-based models provide substantially improved agreement with the reference solution, especially during the early stages of the ULOHS event. These findings highlight the need for validated reactivity models and sufficiently sampled temperature–reactivity data when developing reduced-order methods for microreactor design and safety analysis.

Keywords: Microreactor, Transient, Point-kinetics, Reactivity, Griffin

1. INTRODUCTION

Heat pipe–cooled microreactors (HPMRs) are considered highly promising for remote deployments because they provide inherently passive heat removal and exhibit strong negative reactivity feedback. Because HPMRs are compact and typically employ graphite for moderator, point-kinetics models have become the standard tool for simulating HPMR transient behavior, while spatial dynamic is only leveraged for highly asymmetric scenarios [1, 2]. When employing PKE models for dynamic calculations, reactor designers rely on reactivity models to capture the dependence of neutron population on thermal hydraulic conditions. However, these reactivity models have not undergone extensive validation or verification to ensure they provide accurate and conservative results compared to experiment or spatially-faithful solutions for HPMRs.

In this study, we evaluate the accuracy of four distinct PKE temperature reactivity models against full-core 3D discrete ordinates reference calculations computed with the Griffin deterministic neutronics code [3, 4] and the Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) [5]. The fidelity of each reactivity model is evaluated using an ULOHS transient from the rHPMR benchmark, with all kinetics parameters derived from DFEM- S_n calculations to ensure consistency between the reference solution and the PKE-based models [6]. Furthermore, we perform a sensitivity study on the temperature grid resolution required to inform the reactivity models, ensuring sufficient reactivity data is informing the models.

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The rest of this paper describes the methods and analysis. Section 2 introduces the PKEs and each of the reactivity models under investigation: constant coefficient linear model, linear regression linear model, non-linear regression linear model, and multilinear interpolation model. Section 3.1 contains an overview of the computational models and workflow. Results from the different reactivity models and temperature sampling grids are presented in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 contains conclusions and details plans for future work.

2. THEORY

2.1. Point-Kinetics Equations

The PKEs assume the separability of the angular flux into the product of an amplitude function and a shape function according to Equation (??). Enforcing Equation (??), the time-evolution of $P(t)$ can be obtained as in Ref. [7], using Equations (??) and (??).

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}, t) = P(t)\Psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}) \frac{dP(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho(t) - \beta}{\Lambda} P(t) + \sum_i \lambda_i C_i(t) \frac{dC_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{\beta_i}{\Lambda} P(t) - \lambda_i C_i(t)$$

To enable multiphysics calculations with PKEs, thermal feedback is incorporated by updating the reactivity ρ using temperature information from the coupled thermal model. The specific parameterization of reactivity as a function of temperature is design-dependent and typically reflects the system's actual temperature–reactivity relationship.

2.2. Reactivity Models

To account for temperature effects on neutronics, four reactivity models were defined using average temperatures for the fuel, monolith, and reflector materials. Temperature reactivity data was obtained using DFEM-S_n eigenvalue calculations from 700 K to 1400 K with a temperature increment of 50 K, 100 K, or 175 K for the base discretization case. For a detailed explanation of the DFEM-S_n model refer to the journal paper [4]. The material reactivity contributions are shown in Figure 1. Notably, there is a slight curvature in the fuel reactivity suggesting a square root dependence on fuel temperature akin to the Doppler effects found in commercial light water reactors. An overview of the methods evaluated in this paper is provided below.

2.2.1. Constant Coefficients Linear Model

The simplest method of incorporating temperature feedback into PKE, here named "constant coefficient" method, leverages averaged, material-wise temperature coefficients over the expected range of operation to model the thermal response of the reactor. The coefficients presented in Equation (2) are obtained by independently perturbing each material's temperature while keeping the other materials at 800 K, providing the expected average value at steady state. The temperature subscripts refer to each material with a significant contribution: f for the fuel, m for the graphite moderator, and r for the reflector.

$$\rho(t) [\text{pcm}] = -3.9642(T_f(t) - T_f(0)) - 1.8080(T_m(t) - T_m(0)) + 0.5943(T_r(t) - T_r(0)) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Temperature feedback from each material

2.2.2. Linear Regression Linear Model

An improved method of capturing the reactivity dependence on temperature, here named “linear regression” method consists in generating the constant coefficients through linear regression. The latter aims to generate a “best-fit” of the linear reactivity model onto the actual dependence. The model equation is shown in Equation (3). The best fit is performed by using the Python class `LinearRegression` provided by Scikit-learn [8] that leverages the ordinary least squares method:

$$\rho(t) [\text{pcm}] = -5.0651(T_f(t) - T_f(0)) - 0.7528(T_m(t) - T_m(0)) + 0.6351(T_r(t) - T_r(0)) \quad (3)$$

2.3. Nonlinear Regression Model

A “non-linear regression” model is used to capture the reactivity’s non-linear dependence on the fuel temperature, T_f , and applies the same regression techniques as the linear regression model:

$$\rho(t) [\text{pcm}] = -325.01 \left(\sqrt{T_f(t)} - \sqrt{T_f(0)} \right) - 0.7693 (T_m(t) - T_m(0)) + 0.7066 (T_r(t) - T_r(0)) \quad (4)$$

2.4. Multilinear Piece-wise Interpolation Model

Finally, a multilinear reactivity scheme is employed. This approach captures inter-material feedback effects by interpolating between the nearest temperature state points for all materials. In practice, the Quickhull algorithm [9] is used to generate a three-dimensional polyhedron whose surface facets define interpolation planes. Reactivity values are then obtained via barycentric interpolation within this polyhedron. The multilinear model directly samples temperature-dependent reactivity, with accuracy limited only by the resolution of the underlying temperature grid. As the grid is refined, the multilinear interpolation approaches the true temperature–reactivity behavior. For this reason, the multilinear model was used in the temperature-sampling refinement study to determine the resolution at which further refinement yields negligible accuracy improvements.

3. CODES AND NUMERICAL MODELING

3.1. The Realistic Heat Pipe-cooled Microreactor

The reactivity models were evaluated using the rHPMR benchmark [6], a 5 MW_{th}. As shown in Figure 2, the core consists of 18 hexagonal assemblies surrounded by a beryllium reflector and 12 control drums containing B₄C poison strips. Each assembly houses 19 sodium-filled SS-316 heat pipes and 72 TRISO compacts (19.75% enrichment, 36% packing).

The OpenMC Monte Carlo code [10] was used to compute the multi-group cross section library to be used in Griffin. The library uses an 11-group energy structure found in the benchmark specification [6] with P3 anisotropy and for the operational range of temperatures from 700 K to 1400 K in 100 K isothermal increments. All simulations were performed with 500 total batches, 50 inactive batches, and 100,000 particles per batch using ENDF/B-VIII.0.

Figure 2. OpenMC-generated (a) radial and (b) axial views of the rHPMR benchmark.

To test the reactivity models described in Section 2, an idealized ULOHS transient was selected for this analysis. This choice was made because of the spatially-homogeneous change in thermal conditions during the accident scenario. In this transient, the HTC are reduced uniformly throughout the reactor core to simulate a failure of all the heat pipes. Since the HTC reduction is uniform throughout the core, the neutron flux shape profile responds as uniformly as possible for a realistic transient, a theoretically ideal scenario for application of the PKEs. A full description of the transient can be found in Ref. [4].

3.2. PKE Parameters Calculation

The multiphysics calculations were performed using the coupling scheme presented in Figure 3. First, the DFEM-S_n model computes the point-kinetics parameters shown in Table I by performing forward and adjoint eigenvalue calculations. These kinetic parameters form the basis for the transient simulation, which is carried out through iteration between Griffin and the MOOSE thermal conduction module. At each time step, the thermal model provides average material temperatures, which are then used to update the reactivity. Consistent with the point-kinetics approximation, the spatial power distribution is held fixed throughout the transient. In practice, the steady-state power density from DFEM-S_n is scaled by the PKE-calculated total power and used as input to the conduction solver. The resulting temperature fields are then averaged by material and passed back to the PKE model at each step.

Figure 3. Multiphysics coupling schemes for the PKEs and DFEM- S_n .

4. RESULTS

4.1. Temperature Grid Resolution

A temperature-grid refinement study was performed to find the minimum temperature spacing needed to capture reactivity feedback accurately. The resulting power histories and relative power errors for grid discretizations of 50 K, 100 K, and 175 K are shown in Figure 4. The 175 K increment shows the largest deviation from the reference DFEM- S_n solution. Reducing the temperature spacing to 100 K or 50 K substantially decreases the error, from approximately -23% to about -7.5% for both cases. Little additional improvement is gained when further refining from 100 K to 50 K. Therefore, a 100 K temperature spacing was adopted for the remainder of the study. It is also notable that the bias is consistently negative, which stems from errors in the reactivity model, particularly partial positive reactivity contributions associated with the reflector temperature and the fuel temperature feedback.

4.2. Reactivity Model Comparison

Fig. 5 shows the power response as a function of time for the different model compared with the reference, here denoted as DFEM- S_n . Figs. 6–8 present the corresponding temperature behavior in the fuel, monolith, and reflector, respectively. From Fig. 5, the constant coefficient linear model was the least accurate model with a relative error in the power prediction as high as 24% . Conversely, all other models behaved similarly and agree better with the high-fidelity DFEM- S_n solution. The large discrepancy in the constant coefficient model indicates that the thermal feedback effects are inadequately represented during the ULOHS transient. More importantly, as shown in Figs. 6–8, the model under-predicts the average temperature in all materials, resulting in non-conservative temperature estimates. Although the deviation in average temperature appears modest (about 2%), this metric does not reflect local behavior, where temperature differences as high as 9% may be observed. This underscores the need to

Table I. Kinetics parameters used in the PKE model.

Parameter	Λ (μ s)	λ_1 (1/s)	λ_2 (1/s)	λ_3 (1/s)	λ_4 (1/s)	λ_5 (1/s)	λ_6 (1/s)
Value	164.2	0.01334	0.03274	0.12080	0.30278	0.84949	2.85300
Parameter	β	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4	β_5	β_6
Value (pcm)	669.11	23.076	119.71	114.80	258.58	107.84	45.111

Figure 4. (a) Power and (b) relative error for temperature state point grid coarseness.

incorporate conservatism into the thermal and PKE models to ensure that the design meets safety and performance requirements to mitigate potential temperature underestimation. In particular, the influence of the reflector heating, which produces the oscillation at 800 seconds, requires special attention to correctly capture the reactor dynamic response [6].

Figure 5. (a) Power and (b) relative error for each reactivity model compared to DFEM-S_n.

Figure 6. (a) Fuel temperature and (b) relative error for each reactivity model compared to DFEM-S_n.

Figure 7. (a) Monolith temperature and (b) relative error for each reactivity model compared to DFEM-S_N.

Figure 8. (a) Reflector temperature and (b) relative error for each reactivity model compared to DFEM-S_N.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work evaluated the accuracy of four alternative reactivity models to capture thermal feedbacks in HPMR analysis. A reference DFEM-S_N solution consistent with the PKE model was used to perform the accuracy assessment. The results show that the constant coefficients linear model can produce significant errors. The linear and nonlinear regression-based models show markedly improved agreement against the reference solution, particularly during the early stages of the ULOHS transient. The multilinear model performs comparably and provides the highest accuracy at later times. Collectively, these results highlight the importance of well-constructed reactivity models and sufficient temperature–reactivity state points when developing PKE models for microreactor design and safety analysis.

Future efforts will extend this work beyond the ULOHS scenario to include additional accident scenarios such as Reactivity Insertion Accidents (RIAs) and asymmetric ULOHS transients. The temperature grid refinement will also continue for different resolutions per material to further optimize the models and determine the limits of pre-computation needed to remain accurate. Finally, we will analyze additional iteration schemes, particularly with quasi-static methods, to improve overall accuracy.

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NOMENCLATURE

- $\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}, t)$ Continuous energy angular flux
 β, β_i Total and the i th precursor group delayed neutron fractions
 $C_i(t)$ Delayed neutron precursor concentration for the i th precursor group
 λ_i Decay constant for the i th precursor group
 $P(t)$ Flux amplitude normalized to power
 $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega})$ Static flux shape
 $\rho(t)$ Dynamic reactivity
 Λ Mean neutron generation time
 T_f, T_m, T_r Average fuel, monolith, and reflector temperatures

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